

Pilot Study on the Practice of Animal Research Authorisation Procedures in Germany – A Critical Analysis

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Introduction

Animal research in Germany is subject to strict legal regulation. In 2010, the European Commission adopted Directive 2010/63/EU on the “protection of animals used for scientific purposes”. The aims of the Directive include establishing uniform EU-wide standards for animal welfare in the use of laboratory animals and harmonising the administrative procedures for authorising and monitoring animal research in the Member States. In addition, the Directive seeks to help ensure a level playing field in terms of competitive conditions. The provisions of the EU Directive were transposed into national law in Germany in 2013 with the entry into force of the revised Animal Welfare Act (*Tierschutzgesetz*, TierSchG) and the adoption of the Animal Welfare Laboratory Animal Regulation (*Tierschutz-Versuchstierverordnung*, TierSchVersV). TierSchG and TierSchVersV were amended in 2021 in response to infringement proceedings initiated by the EU. Further legal and administrative provisions governing the conduct of animal research are set out in TierSchVersV and in the Regulation on the Notification of Experimental Animals (*Versuchstiermeldeverordnung*, VersTierMeldV), while guidance on the interpretation and implementation of TierSchG and TierSchVersV is provided by the General Administrative Regulation on the Implementation of the Animal Welfare Act (*Allgemeine Verwaltungsvorschrift zur Durchführung des Tierschutzgesetzes*, AVV). The latter dates from 2000, however, and has not yet been updated to reflect the current legal situation. Practical implementation of the statutory and administrative provisions is the responsibility of the individual federal states and their competent authorities.

Directive 2010/63/EU introduced numerous new and more specific requirements. Among other things, it set out new provisions governing the application procedures and authorisation procedures required for animal research projects. These include a deadline of 40 working days (with a one-time extension of up to 15 working days permitted in exceptional cases): within this period, the competent authority is required to process an application and inform the applicant of its approval or rejection (Article 41(1) of Directive 2010/63/EU; Section 32(1) TierSchVersV).

After an investigation of the situation regarding administrative authorisation procedures for animal research in Germany, the DFG’s Permanent Senate Commission on Animal Research (SKTF) issued a statement¹ in 2018 indicating that there were serious procedural problems, including the following in particular:

- ▶ delays in authorisation procedures, in some cases substantially exceeding the statutory processing deadline;

¹ DFG, Permanent Senate Commission on Animal Research (2018): [Genehmigungsverfahren für Tierversuche – Stellungnahme](#) (German only).

- ▶ a sharp increase in the administrative workload;
- ▶ legal uncertainty in numerous procedural and substantive matters.

These issues have had a significant impact on research projects:

- ▶ scientific progress has been impeded due to delays;
- ▶ Germany's competitive standing as a research location has suffered and competitive conditions across federal states are unequal;
- ▶ early-career researchers are suffering specific disadvantages as fixed-term employment contracts are time-limited (usually to a maximum of 5 years).

Since feedback from the research community has indicated that the core problems outlined in the statement continue to persist, the SKTF has conducted this pilot study in order to establish a comprehensive dataset that, for the first time, enables the progress of authorisation procedures to be tracked across specific stages of processing based on quantitative data. The analysis provides insights into the current situation regarding the duration of authorisation procedures and the practical implementation of the legal provisions by the competent authorities in the federal states.

Methodology

Data collection

The data were collected by consulting animal welfare officers (TierSchB) or the corresponding institutional bodies at academic university and non-university research institutions. They have in-depth knowledge of the authorisation processes for animal experiments at their institutions and access to the relevant data.

In December 2023, a detailed questionnaire was sent by e-mail to 157 institutions in Germany, accompanied by a brief project description and explanatory notes as an aid to completion. In cases where more than one contact address for an animal welfare officer (or the corresponding institutional body) was available, all addresses were contacted. Participation was voluntary.

Participants were asked to retrospectively provide data on the ten most recent applications they had processed and completed (applications for authorisation, applications under the simplified authorisation procedure, collective applications, notifications and amendment applications) (see **Table 1A**). It was also possible to submit information on fewer than ten applications, depending on data availability. The data supplied did not allow any inference to be drawn as to the content of the applications or the identity of the applicants. In addition, general information on the authorisation procedure was collected on an optional basis using predefined response categories

(Table 1B, see Annex). Respondents were also able to provide additional information on the authorisation procedure in free-text answers. While the federal state of the respective institution had to be specified, stating the name of the institution, the competent authority and the position of the person completing the questionnaire was optional.

A – Data on the authorisation procedure for individual applications
Date of submission of the application
Date of confirmation of receipt
Date of confirmation of completeness by the authority
Date of receipt of first queries*
Date of submission of responses to first queries*
Number of first queries*
Date of receipt of authorisation/rejection
Type of application
Does the application concern training, continuing education or advanced training?
[optional] authorised/rejected
[optional] number of hearings, interviews, etc. where applicable

Table 1A: Overview of data requested on the authorisation procedure for individual applications.

*Since more than one set of queries is often raised in relation to a single application (commonly referred to as “rounds of queries” or “query rounds”), it was possible to enter data for up to six such rounds per application. This table provides an example showing only the data requested for one round of queries.

The questionnaire was created using standard software (MS Excel 2016, Microsoft Office Professional Plus 2016) and could be completed using compatible programme versions. The completed questionnaires were returned by e-mail. Each questionnaire was checked for technical correctness (e.g. compatible formatting for further analysis, spelling errors).

Data analysis

All questionnaires were anonymised prior to analysis. The analyses were conducted in MATLAB (Version R2023b Update 4). Based on the collected data, various time spans within the application process were calculated (see **Figure 1**). All data refers to dates on which documents were sent to or received from the authority. In determining these time spans, only the authority’s working days were taken into account. To calculate the “net processing time” (or “net working

days”) by the authorities, the working days that applicants required to respond to queries were subtracted.

As an authority may issue several sets of queries during the application process, there may be more than one query round per application. The net processing time was defined as the period in working days between a start date (e.g. confirmation of receipt) and an end date (e.g. date of receipt of approval or rejection), minus the working days taken up by all query rounds. The time spans for analysis were selected to reflect the multi-stage nature of the application process as precisely as possible. In some cases, it was not possible to provide all requested data because information on individual process stages was not available or certain stages (such as confirmation of completeness) were not part of the authority’s established practice. In addition to the time spans representing the net processing time on the part of the authorities, the analysis also included the time taken by applicants to respond to queries (“response time”), the number of queries per application and the number of query rounds.

Figure 1: Dates and time spans during the course of the authorisation process.

Date A – date of submission of the application, date B – date of confirmation of receipt, date C – date of confirmation of completeness by the authority, date D – date of receipt of approval or rejection, date E – period during which queries were raised. Based on these dates, six time spans were calculated: Time span I (dark blue): A–D, time span II (blue): B–D, time span III (turquoise): C–D, time span IV (dark green): A–B, time span V (green): A–C, time span VI (light green): B–C. In addition, time spans were calculated for the time taken by applicants to respond to queries. For each query round, the time span was defined as the period between the date of receipt of the queries and the date on which the responses were sent.

Further correlation analyses were conducted (in each case with an indication of the Spearman correlation coefficient r) between (i) the number of queries per application and the applicant response time, (ii) the number of queries per application and the net processing time taken by the

authorities, and (iii) the applicant response time and the net processing time taken by the authorities. The data listed in **Table 1B** was also analysed.

All results were processed descriptively and presented in the form of histograms, box plots or bar charts. Further details are provided in the respective figure legends. Normal distribution was tested using a Kolmogorov–Smirnov test (kstest; MATLAB, Version R2023b Update 4). Data that follows a normal distribution is indicated accordingly.

Given the voluntary nature of participation and the uneven response rate, the sample sizes vary considerably between federal states. The findings should therefore be regarded as a reflection of trends rather than a comprehensive, statistically significant depiction of administrative processes across Germany as a whole. The data available does not permit systematic comparative statistical analysis. Since this is the first survey of its kind, it cannot yet offer insights into long-term developments. The collection of quantitative data would need to be carried out on a regular basis in order to capture developments of this kind in connection with authorisation procedures.

Results

Of the 157 institutions contacted, 44 returned a total of 51 completed questionnaires. In the case of some institutions with multiple contact addresses, more than one questionnaire was returned. Manual verification of the questionnaires was carried out to ensure that no data relating to a single authorisation procedure was counted twice. Data was submitted from all federal states with the exception of two (see **Table 2**).

For each questionnaire, datasets were available for up to ten applications (see Methodology). Datasets for 466 applications were submitted in total.

Federal states	Number of completed questionnaires [n]	Number of applications analysed [n]
BB (Brandenburg)	1	7
BE (Berlin)	5	45
BW (Baden-Württemberg)	8	76
BY (Bavaria)	9	88
HB (Bremen)	1	8
HE (Hesse)	4	40
HH (Hamburg)	1	5
MV (Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania)	4	40
NI (Lower Saxony)	3	30
NW (North Rhine-Westphalia)	6	60
RP (Rhineland-Palatinate)	4	29
SH (Schleswig-Holstein)	-	-
SL (Saarland)	-	-
SN (Saxony)	1	10
ST (Saxony-Anhalt)	3	26
TH (Thuringia)	1	2
Total	51	466

Table 2: Overview of the number of completed questionnaires and applications analysed by federal state. The federal states are listed alphabetically according to their abbreviations. No responses were received from Schleswig-Holstein or Saarland. In the figures below, the federal states are referred to exclusively by their abbreviations.

Most of the data collected relates to applications for authorisation of an experiment involving animals (“authorisation applications”) under Section 31 of the Animal Protection Laboratory Animal Regulation (TierSchVersV) (397 out of 466). 24 and 37 datasets were submitted for applications under the simplified authorisation procedure (Section 36 TierSchVersV) and amendment applications (Section 34 TierSchVersV) respectively. Ten datasets were submitted without information on the type of application. No datasets were received for collective applications (Section 37 TierSchVersV) or notifications concerning the use of decapods (Section 39 TierSchVersV). The data was analysed separately according to the type of application. Unless otherwise indicated, the analyses shown refer exclusively to data on authorisation applications under Section 31 TierSchVersV.

For time span I (date of submission of the application – date of receipt of approval or rejection), the net processing time by the authority has a median of 56.5 working days for 390 authorisation applications (data required to calculate the time span was not available in the case of seven applications) (see **Figure 2A**).

The range of results is very wide, with a minimum of nine and a maximum of 621 net working days. In addition, a comparison of results for time span I between the federal states (see **Figure 3A**) shows that this period varies considerably depending on the state.

Figure 2: Net processing time of authorisation applications under Section 31 TierSchVersV by the authorities, in working days (WD), for (A) time span I (date of submission of the application – date of receipt of approval or rejection, dark blue), (B) time span II (date of confirmation of receipt – date of receipt of approval or rejection, blue), and (C) time span III (date of confirmation of completeness by the authority – date of receipt of approval or rejection, turquoise). The data is shown in the form of histograms with 10-day class intervals. With reference to the 40-day deadline (Section 32(3) TierSchVersV), a processing time of 40 WD is marked by a red line. Net processing times exceeding 40 WD are shown in grey in the histograms. The X-axis shows the number of working days, while the Y-axis shows the number of authorisation applications. The figure also indicates the median, mean, minimum (min) and maximum (max) values. The number of analysable applications relative to the total number (x out of 397) is shown in the pie chart (the red segment represents the proportion of applications not included in the histogram relative to the total). For better visualisation of the histograms, the X-axis is truncated at 250 WD (this means that in histogram A, data from two applications is not shown; in histogram B, data from one application is not shown).

For time span II (date of confirmation of receipt – date of receipt of approval or rejection), the median net processing time was 46.0 working days (see **Figure 2B**). Similar to time span I, time span II also shows a very wide range of results, with a minimum of six and a maximum of 262 net working days. This considerable heterogeneity for time span II is likewise reflected in the comparison between federal states (see **Figure 3B**). Time span III (date of confirmation of completeness by the authority – date of receipt of approval or rejection) most closely corresponds to the period for which the statutory 40-day deadline applies (Section 32(3) TierSchVersV). The median for time span III is 35.0 net working days, again with a wide range of results – from a minimum of one to a maximum of 174 working days (see **Figure 2C**). However, it should be noted that the total number of datasets evaluated here (187 out of 397 applications) is considerably lower than for time spans I and II. This is primarily due to the fact that some state authorities do

not issue confirmation of completeness for applications. Consequently, it was not possible to provide any information on this time span for certain federal states (e.g. BW, SC in **Figure 3C**). The heterogeneity between federal states is also evident for time span III (see **Figure 3C**).

Figure 3: Net processing time of authorisation applications under Section 31 TierSchVersV by the authorities, in working days (WD), broken down by federal state in alphabetical order, for (A) time span I (date of submission of the application – date of receipt of approval or rejection, dark blue), (B) time span II (date of confirmation of receipt – date of receipt of approval or rejection, blue), and (C) time span III (date of confirmation of completeness by the authority – date of receipt of approval or rejection, turquoise). The data is presented as box plots showing the median, 25th and 75th percentiles, minimum and maximum (as whiskers), and outliers. The 40-day deadline (Section 32(3) TierSchVersV) is shown as a reference line on the Y-axis. The colour coding of the box plots corresponds to that used for the time spans in Figure 1. Saarland (SL) and Schleswig-Holstein (SH) are not shown due to the lack of responses. The amount of data from Thuringia was insufficient to display as a box plot.

Date B (date of confirmation of receipt; see **Figure 1**) is specified in the legal framework of the authorisation procedure: under Section 32 (2) TierSchVersV, the authorities are required to issue confirmation of receipt of an application “without delay”. This period is represented by time span IV (date of submission of the application – date of confirmation of receipt): it shows a median of 7.0 net working days, with a substantial spread ranging from a minimum of one day to a maximum of 508 days (see **Figure 4A**).

Time spans V (date of submission of the application – date of confirmation of completeness) and VI (date of confirmation of receipt – date of confirmation of completeness) both relate to the completeness of applications and show medians of 9.0 and 1.5 net working days (see **Figure 4B and C**), with a minimum of one net working day and maximum values of 218 and 194 net working days respectively. Here too, the number of datasets recorded (188 and 182 out of 397) is considerably lower than the total number of applications (397), since confirmation of completeness is not issued by all authorities. When the data for time spans IV, V and VI are broken down by federal state, a similarly heterogeneous pattern is observed (see **Figure 5A–C**).

Figure 4: Net processing time of authorisation applications under Section 31 TierSchVersV by the authorities, in working days (WD), for (A) time span IV (date of submission of the application – date of confirmation of receipt, dark green), (B) time span V (date of submission of the application – date of confirmation of completeness by the authority, green), and (C) time span VI (date of confirmation of receipt – date of confirmation of completeness by the authority, light green). The data is shown in the form of histograms with 10-day class intervals. The X-axis shows the number of WD, the Y-axis the number of authorisation applications. The figure also indicates the median, mean, minimum (min) and maximum (max) values. The number of applications suitable for analysis, compared to the total number (x of 397), is depicted in the pie chart (the red segment represents the proportion of applications not included in the histogram relative to the total). The colour coding of the histograms corresponds to that used for the time spans in Figure 1. For improved visualisation of the histograms, the X-axis is truncated at 250 WD (this means that in histogram A, the processing time for one application is not shown; in B and C, three applications are not shown in each case).

Figure 5: Net processing time of authorisation applications under Section 31 TierSchVersV by the authorities, in working days (WD), broken down by federal state in alphabetical order, for (A) time span IV (date of submission of the application – date of confirmation of receipt, dark green), (B) time span V (date of submission of the application – date of confirmation of completeness by the authority, green), and (C) time span VI (date of confirmation of receipt – date of confirmation of completeness by the authority, light green). The data is presented as box plots showing the median, 25th and 75th percentiles, minimum and maximum (as whiskers), and outliers. For improved visual representation, HB (in histogram A) and ST (in histograms B and C) are shown on a separate Y-axis (left, grey).

In addition to determining the time spans within the authorisation procedures (for applications under Section 31 TierSchVersV), the number of queries and query rounds was also analysed (see **Figure 6A and B**). The number of queries raised by the authorities shows a considerable range, from a minimum of one to a maximum of 119, with a median of 13 queries (see **Figure 6A**). The number of query rounds varies from zero to five, with a median of two rounds (see **Figure 6B**). No queries were reported in the case of 94 applications (23.7 per cent). In 80 out of 397 applications, there were more than two query rounds. 11 queries were raised per round on average. A comparison of the number of queries and query rounds between federal states shows that some state authorities tend to raise particularly extensive queries, while others require less clarification (see **Figure 7A and B**).

Figure 6: (A) Number of queries raised by the authority per application and (B) number of query rounds per application. The data is shown in the form of histograms with class intervals of five days (A) and one query round (B). The Y-axis shows the number of authorisation applications. The figure also indicates the median, mean, minimum (min) and maximum (max) values (in A).

Figure 7: (A) Number of queries raised by the authority per application and (B) number of query rounds per application, each broken down by federal state in alphabetical order. The data is presented as box plots showing the median, 25th and 75th percentiles, minimum and maximum (as whiskers), and outliers.

The time applicants required to respond to queries (“response time”) was also analysed here. The median response time was 11 working days, with a minimum of one and a maximum of 214 working days.

A comparison between the total number of queries per application and the number of working days required by applicants to respond shows that a higher number of queries per application does not necessarily result in longer response times ($r = 0.49$; see **Figure 8A**). Similarly, it was not possible to establish a clear link between the number of queries per application and time span I (date of submission of the application – date of receipt of approval or rejection) as the net processing time by the authorities, or between response time and time span I ($r = 0.28$ and $r = 0.23$ respectively; see **Figure 8B and C**).

Figure 8: Spearman rank correlation analyses between (A) number of queries per application and response time, (B) number of queries per application and time span I (date of submission of the application – date of receipt of approval or rejection), and (C) response time and time span I; r = rank correlation coefficient.

As shown in **Table 1B**, some additional information on the authorisation process was also collected. These results are summarised as bar charts in **Figure 9** and are discussed below, together with information provided in the free-text fields.

Confirmations of receipt (under Section 32 (2) TierSchVersV) are issued in all federal states (see **Figure 9A**). The procedures followed by the authorities vary, however. According to the additional information provided by some respondents, applicants have to actively request confirmation in certain cases, whereas elsewhere, the confirmation is issued automatically by the authority. Some authorities only issue confirmation after a (formal) review of the application, while in some cases the confirmation already includes the future file reference number of the procedure.

There are also marked differences in how applications can be submitted (see **Figure 9B**). Some authorities still require multiple printed copies of the application to be submitted by post. Only one federal state has introduced an online tool for submission.

Figure 9: Analysis of the additional information on the authorisation procedure (see Table 1B). The data is presented in the form of bar charts, with each bar representing one of the predefined response options. The X-axis shows the number of responses submitted (N/A indicates that no answer was selected).

The levying of fees for authorisation applications is carried out relatively consistently and follows the applicable administrative fee regulations of the respective federal state (see **Figure 9C**). Nevertheless, there are differences between federal states in how fees are calculated and also in terms of the final amounts charged. Some authorities apply fixed lump-sum fees, while others calculate fees based on the amount of work involved. According to the information available from this survey, the fees per application range between €117.50 and €5,600.00. Based on the responses received, the average fee is approximately €600.

The responses concerning the 40-day deadline (Section 32 (1) TierSchVersV) indicate that this period usually begins with confirmation of completeness (see **Figure 9D**). In some cases, however, the exact starting point of the deadline is not known. There is considerable variation in the authorities' understanding of when an application is deemed complete (see **Figure 9E**). In most cases, formal completeness is the deciding factor, while in others, substantive completeness is required or other criteria are applied. Several authorities include consultation with the animal experiments commission in accordance with Section 15 TierSchG when determining completeness. One authority states that (substantive) completeness can only be established at the end of the entire process and therefore coincides with the final decision on the application. Further information from the free-text fields indicated that in the case of one authority, the 40-day

period does not begin until after the applicant has responded to the first set of queries, for example. Where no confirmation of completeness is issued, the start of the 40-day period remains entirely unclear.

In addition to the differing interpretations of completeness, there are also variations in how authorities handle query rounds within the framework of the 40-day period (see **Figure 9F**). Some respondents indicate that the deadline is paused or restarted when queries are raised, but most state that the 40-day period is not recalculated in the event of queries.

Discussion

This pilot study is based on a detailed survey of the authorisation procedures for animal experiments. It provides extensive information on the procedural workflow and specific data on individual process stages. Drawing on the data available, it is possible to identify three main areas of concern that result in delays, a substantial administrative workload and a lack of planning reliability for researchers: 1) the duration of authorisation procedures, 2) the number of queries and query rounds and 3) differences in procedure between the competent authorities.

1) Duration of authorisation procedures

With regard to the duration of the application process, particular attention is given to the statutory 40-day period for deciding on an application, which may be extended once by 15 working days in justified cases (Section 32 TierSchVersV). The data show that time span III, which most closely corresponds to this legally prescribed period, has a median of 35.0 net working days (mean: 38.3 net working days). Looking beyond the summary statistics to the full range shown in the histograms, it emerges that this period is sometimes substantially exceeded. According to the statutory provisions, one would expect a clear cut-off at 40 days (see **Figure 2C**). This is not the case, however. In fact, 74 out of 187 applications (39.6 per cent) exceed the 40-day period. 26 applications (13.9 per cent) require a net processing time of more than 55 days (40 days plus a 15-day extension), and in the case of six applications (3.2 per cent), the net processing time exceeds 100 days.

One particularly critical point is that for more than half of the datasets submitted (210 out of 397), it was not possible to analyse this time span because no date for confirmation of completeness was provided. Responses on procedural practice indicate that some authorities do not issue confirmation of completeness at all, or only after extensive substantive assessment (see **Figure 9B**).

In such cases, it is not possible to determine whether processing occurred within the prescribed timeframe of 40 days. Thus, due to the unclear definition of “completeness” and divergent administrative practices of individual authorities, a reliable evaluation of compliance with the 40-day deadline – the sole legally defined time limit in the authorisation process – is not feasible. A binding definition of this process stage is urgently required so as to ensure the procedure is consistent and reliable. In line with the practice followed by most authorities, the term “completeness” should mean that all necessary documents and information have been submitted, i.e. the application is formally complete. Confirmation of completeness to applicants should be mandatory for all authorities.

Feedback from the research community increasingly identifies the duration of authorisation procedures as a problem. Although a large proportion of applications formally fall within the 40-day period when time span III is considered, the key factor for researchers is not this single procedural stage but the total duration of the process – from the submission of the application through to the final decision: after all, experiments cannot be carried out during this period and research projects cannot progress (see **Figure 2A**). A planned research project, for which project-specific funding has often already been secured, can commence only upon receipt of authorisation.

The median overall duration of the procedure (time span I) determined in this pilot study is 56.5 net working days (mean: 69.1), in other words approximately two-and-a-half to three calendar months. If the total processing time is considered without subtracting query rounds, the median rises to 85 working days (mean: 98), or roughly five months. Maximum values – the three longest net processing times of 621, 269 and 224 days (around 28, 13 and 11 months respectively) – show that in individual cases the overall process can take an exceptionally long time. Given that most research projects and their funding are geared towards periods of three to four years, such long and often unpredictable processing times impair research performance in a competitive environment. In a worst-case scenario, previously approved funding may have to be withdrawn. A lack of predictability and long delays can cause serious problems, particularly for research consortia, since the individual projects can no longer be reliably coordinated.

It is also problematic that the distribution and average net processing time vary considerably between federal states (see **Figures 3 and 5**). Particularly lengthy and complex procedures can diminish the attractiveness of certain research locations and prompt researchers to relocate. Outsourcing animal experiments to other countries not only undermines Germany’s research competitiveness, it also entails a loss of sovereignty over animal welfare standards, which are particularly high in Germany.

2) Number of queries and query rounds

Another recurring point of criticism among applicants concerns the required level of detail in authorisation applications and the depth of scrutiny applied by authorities. While detailed assessment to safeguard animal welfare is understandable, increasing levels of procedural detail without any obvious bearing on specific aspects of animal welfare are not. As one indicator of the degree of procedural detail, this pilot study examined the number of queries raised (see **Figure 7**). The average number of queries per application is 19 (median: 13) across two query rounds, though the data indicates substantial variation. For a significant number of applications the number of queries is considerably higher: 40 applications (10.1 per cent) involved more than 40 queries.

There are also marked differences between authorities, with a particularly high volume of queries in certain federal states. It is not possible to reliably derive a clear explanation of these differences from the data collected for this pilot study. However, it does not seem likely that poor quality of applications is the deciding factor here: it is improbable that only in certain federal states do applications exhibit such significant quality deficits that a high number of queries are necessary to compensate for these alleged quality deficits. Rather, it is reasonable to assume that a high number of queries reflects the procedural practice of the authority in question.

In order to assess the potential impact of the number of queries on the authorisation procedure, the time applicants took to respond was analysed and compared with the authorities' processing times (see **Figure 8**). On average, applicants took 17 working days per query round to respond to the queries raised. A closer look shows that the number of queries per application only partly correlates with the applicants' response time: the data demonstrates that even a large number of queries can be answered promptly by applicants. The data further shows that neither the number of queries per application nor the time required by applicants to respond has a systematic impact on the authorities' processing times. A rapid response by applicants does not necessarily mean swift processing on the part of the authorities – and vice versa. It is not possible to derive a clear explanation of this finding from the data collected since various factors may play a role, such as the complexity of the queries, the applicants' availability to respond and the capacity of the authorities to process the applications. However, it is undisputed that each additional query round entails extra work and prolongs the overall procedure.

3) Differences in procedure between the competent authorities

Substantial differences between the federal states are evident throughout the dataset, whether in processing times (see **Figures 2–5**), in the number of queries (see **Figure 7**) or in terms of the formal procedural stages (see **Figure 9**). These discrepancies between authorities and federal states can make some research locations less attractive, with consequences ranging from relocation to other federal states to the migration of research activities away from Germany altogether. Moreover, the lack of harmonisation in the implementation of legal requirements runs counter to the fundamental aim of EU Directive 2010/63, namely to ensure equal conditions for animal research across Europe and counteract disparities in competition.

Even though the data collected in this pilot study does not permit specific causes to be identified for the procedural differences observed, the results clearly demonstrate the urgent need to standardise authorisation procedures. One key aspect here is the unambiguous definition of “completeness” and the point at which a confirmation of receipt is issued. The European Commission’s second implementation report (2024)² shows that Germany – alongside Malta – is one of only two EU Member States that do not provide the competent authorities with supporting tools (such as checklists for project evaluation) to promote consistent practice in the authorisation process.

One appropriate instrument for harmonising administrative and formal processes between the federal states could potentially be the General Administrative Regulation (*Allgemeine Verwaltungsvorschrift*, AVV). The AVV serves as a guideline for authorities and other parties involved in the process (animal welfare officers, applicants) with the aim of supporting the administrative implementation of legal provisions and ensuring a uniform procedure. However, it has not been updated for 24 years to reflect the subsequent amendments to the Animal Welfare Act (*Tierschutzgesetz*, TierSchG). It should therefore be adapted to the current legal framework as a matter of urgency. In addition, further tools should be made available to harmonise and align the content and level of detail of the review procedures across the federal states. Checklists or nationally standardised application forms could contribute to this. It would also be desirable for authorities to further digitalise the application submission process and introduce electronic

² In addition to a wide range of data on the implementation of Directive 2010/63/EU in the EU Member States, the two implementation reports issued by the European Commission present basic figures on the number of authorisation applications submitted and the length of processing times in different countries. However, the lack of metadata on methods (such as data acquisition and analysis) makes meaningful comparison with the data gathered in this study very challenging. Therefore, this study does not attempt a direct comparison or further interpretation of the results from the Implementation Reports. The reports are available for download at https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/chemicals/animals-science_en.

documentation of ongoing authorisations (should be made available also in English), so that possible changes can be tracked more easily.

Conclusion

This pilot study provides the first extensive set of data on authorisation procedures for animal experiments in academic research in Germany. Based on this detailed survey, it was possible to analyse specific procedural time spans and document differences in administrative practice between the federal states.

The results highlight key administrative challenges that increasingly impede research activity. Drawing on these findings, the SKTF has simultaneously issued a statement³ in which it sets out a series of urgent recommendations for action addressed to the competent ministries and authorities at both federal and state level, including the following in particular:

- ▶ a reduction of the bureaucratic workload,
- ▶ the acceleration of procedures, and
- ▶ the national harmonisation of procedures.

A regularly recurring survey of quantitative data, as conducted in this pilot study, should be established in order to monitor the development of authorisation procedures over the long term – including for the purposes of the planned evaluation following the amendment of the Animal Welfare Act (*Tierschutzgesetz*, TierSchG) in 2021⁴.

³ DFG, Permanent Senate Commission on Animal Research (2025): Animal Research Authorisation Procedures – Where Things Stand and What Needs to Change, [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17177762](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17177762).

⁴ BT-Drs 19/27626, Begründung des Gesetzentwurfs, [Explanatory Memorandum to the Draft Bill], p. 17.

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Annex:

B – Additional information	
	<i>default choices</i>
How is an application submitted?	By mail Digital & by mail Digital (e-mail) Digital (other format)
Is a confirmation of receipt issued?	Yes No I don't know
When is an application considered complete?	Substantive completeness Formal completeness After review by advisory commission (Section 15 TierSchG) Other I don't know No receipt of completeness is provided
When does the 40-day deadline begin?	Date of submission of the application Date of confirmation of receipt Date of confirmation of completeness Other I don't know No information is provided by authorities
Is the 40-day deadline recalculated in the event of queries?	Yes, the 40-days are paused Yes, the 40-days are re-started No Other I don't know
Are there any fees?	Yes No Partly (please explain) I don't know
If so, what is the fee per application?	
Please describe the authorisation process with the steps of interaction between your institution and your authority in brief keywords in the text field below	

Table 1B: Overview of the additional information requested on the authorisation procedure. Each question offered multiple response options, of which only one could be selected. Respondents could also provide further information in free-text form. Answering these questions was optional.

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